

Majhera 3, a drought-tolerant variety

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During kharif 1978, 3 upland trials consisting of 121 early maturing entries were direct-seeded at the Rice Research

Station, Majhera. Intermittent drought periods of 8, 9, and 10 days, separated by 5- to 6-day intervals, occurred during the vegetative growth stage. At the reproductive and grain-filling stages, drought struck twice for periods of 14 and 6 days, separated by a 4-day interval.

At maturity only the variety Majhera 3, a selection from the local variety Jaulia, matured and had good

seed setting. None of the other 120 varieties performed well, although a few had seed setting. Majhera 3 is a tall, nonlodging type in uplands. Its medium slender grain has straw-colored husk and a red pericarp. It is susceptible to both leaf and neck blast. Its drought tolerance should be tested in other agroclimatic regions. □

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Research on varietal tolerance for phosphorus-deficient rice soils

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Phosphorus (P) deficiency appears to be the most widespread of several soil mineral stresses that limit rice yields in many rice-growing countries. Recent screening has shown that some varieties are tolerant of P deficiency. Use of varietal tolerance to stabilize rice yields would be simpler and less expensive than P amendment, especially in soils with mild mineral deficiencies.

IRRI conducted a performance test on a P-deficient soil (available P, 2 ppm) in the 1978 dry season at Pangil, Laguna province, Philippines, to measure how much P deficiency reduces yields and to assess the potential of varietal tolerance. Twenty-four tolerant and susceptible genotypes of comparable growth duration were used in the test. Rices tolerant of P deficiency were chosen after careful review of screening results for several seasons. The susceptible rices chosen had all exhibited high yield potential in rice yield trials. Half of the experimental site, referred to as P₁, received a basal application of 25 kg P₂O₅/ha. The untreated half was P₀. Eighteen-day-old seedlings were transplanted on 3 February 1978 at 25- × 25-cm spacing at 60 hills/plot, in

a randomized complete block design replicated S times on P₀ and P₁. A basal application of urea at 50 kg N/ha was made at final land preparation. Recommended management practices were followed until maturity. The entries were scored for injury due to P deficiency on 17 March and 8 May. Grain, yield and ancillary characters, such as number of panicles, straw weight,

and P content of grain and straw were recorded.

Treatment differences in yield were significant at both P levels (see table). For P₁ the yields ranged from 2.6 to 4.3 t/ha (mean, 3.9 t/ha); for P₀, they ranged from 3.6 to 4.0 t/ha (mean, 3.3 t/ha). The yield was 15% lower in P₀ than in P₁. The yield depression ranged from 4.3 to 26.7% for individual varieties. But

Performance of 24 rices on a phosphorus (P)-deficient soil at Pangil, Laguna province, Philippines, 1978 dry season.

Designation	Grain yield ^a (g/plot)		Yield difference ^b (%) (P ₁ -P ₀)
	P ₁	P ₀	
IR8	791 cdefg	736 abcd	7.0
IR34	877 a	812 a	7.4*
IR40	786 cdefg	620 efghi	21.1*
IR1514A-E666	784 cdefg	585 ghij	25.4**
IR1623-93-2-2	759 defg	619 efghi	18.4**
IR2061-628-1-6-4-3	841 abcd	713 bcde	15.4**
IR2307-84-2-1	797 bcdefg	672 cdefg	15.7*
IR2797-105-2-2	875 ab	709 bcdef	19.0**
IR2797-105-2-2-3	795 cdefg	761 abc	4.3
IR2823-103-5-1A	848 abc	732 abcd	13.7**
IR2823-103-5-1B	849 abc	741 abcd	12.7**
IR2863-35-3-3	792 cdefg	688 ef	13.1**
IR3449-172-2	718 g	611 fghi	14.9*
IR4219-35-3	528 h	516 j	2.3
IR4422-51-6-3	784 cdefg	575 ghij	26.7**
IR4427-58-5-2A	808 abcdef	671 cdefgh	17.0*
IR4427-58-5-28	794 cdefg	670 cdefgh	15.6*
IR4427-315-2-3	764 defg	695 bcdef	9.0
IR4432-38-6-5-2	740 fg	644 defghi	13.0*
IR4707-123-3A	760 defg	571 ij	24.9**
IR4707-123-3B	756 efg	630 efghi	16.7*
IR4816-70-1	822 abcdef	685 ef	16.7*
IR5105-93-2-2	771 cdefg	669 cdefgh	13.2
BR51-91-6	834 abcde	790 ab	5.3

^aP₁ received a basal application of 25 kg P₂O₅/ha. P₀ received no P. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^b*Significant at 5% level; **significant at 1% level.

the yield of six cultures — IR8, IR2797-105-2-2-3, IR4219-35-3, IR4427-315-2-3, BR51-91-6, and IR5105-93-2-2 — were not significantly lower in P₀ and P₁. BR51-91-6 performed best in both P₀ and P₁.

Other top yielders were IR34, IR2823-103-5-1A, and IR2823-103-5-1B, but yields between the two levels differed significantly. Panicle numbers were significantly lower in P₀ than in P₁ in IR20, IR2823-103-5-1A, and IR1514A-E666. Straw production was considerably lower in P₀ in four cultures:

IR2061-628-1-6-4-3, IR2823-103-5-1A, IR1514A-E666, and IR2797-105-2-2.

Varietal differences were found in P content of grain and straw. But P content was not related to varietal reaction to P deficiency.

Field observations showed that early growth was suppressed considerably in P₀ because of P deficiency, and that genotypes varied in degree of suppression. But the visible differences lessened after the maximum tillering stage and were minimum by flowering. Furthermore, flowering was delayed from 2 to 9 days

in many entries in P₀. The late-maturing cultures may recover better from initial depression (caused by P deficiency) than the early maturing ones.

Overall, IR34, BR51-91-6, and IR1505-93-2-2 could be regarded as tolerant. Six others, IR40, IR1514A-E666, IR2061-628-1-6-4-3, IR2823-103-5-1A, IR2797-105-2-2, and IR4707-123-3A could be considered sensitive.

The test is being repeated in the 1978 wet season. □

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Rice cold tolerance workshop in Korea

Scientists from six national programs and IRRI participated in a workshop on cold tolerance in rice in the Republic of Korea, 16-19 September 1978. The workshop was sponsored by the Korean Office of Rural Development (ORD) and the UNDP-funded International Rice Testing Program (IRTP), coordinated by IRRI. Before the workshop, some of the scientists participated in an IRTP cold tolerance monitoring tour in the Indian states of Kashmir and Himachal Pradesh, and in Nepal.

Rice in the temperate areas and in many high-elevation areas in the tropics suffers from cool temperature during the seeding stage or at flowering. Most rice farmers in the temperate regions grow japonica varieties, but tropical farmers prefer indicas. Indicas have higher yield potential but they are more susceptible to cool temperature. Cooperative efforts are needed to combine the cold tolerance of japonica varieties with the high yield potential of the indica varieties.

Korean scientists have crossed indica and japonica germplasm to develop high yielding rice varieties with japonica grain quality and some cold tolerance. They have developed techniques to systematically evaluate their breeding materials for cold tolerance and have

successfully integrated research with extension and farmers' training programs to implement research results quickly. Consequently, Korean rice production has increased dramatically since 1970.

In 1977 national rice yields were the highest in the world — average of 4.94 t/ha of milled rice. Thus, it was fitting that Korea host the first International Rice Cold Tolerance Workshop.

The objective of the workshop and the IRTP monitoring tour was to review the current status of breeding for cold tolerance and to evaluate entries in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN). ORD Director General In Hwan Kim challenged the group to develop better varieties with cold tolerance, blast resistance, and acceptable grain quality. He said that although Korean production had increased substantially, the process of varietal improvement is continuous and never ending. Speakers from the various countries outlined their cold temperature problems and current research programs.

Participants made the following recommendations to improve collaboration work and speed the development of cold-tolerant varieties;

1. The rice growing environment of cool areas should be characterized.
2. Screening methodologies should be improved and expanded.

3. The rapid generation advance (RGA) method should be used to rapidly develop more diverse germplasm.

4. The IRCTN should be reorganized to maximize the utilization of nursery entries.

5. Young scientists from the cool regions should participate as a group in the GEU training program so they can become acquainted with new cold-tolerance screening methodology and share professional experiences. □

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